

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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Virtual Lecture Series

Innovation

DELIVERABLE 5.1
MONTH 18

D5.1 – Virtual Lecture Series *Innovation*

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I. General

A. Summary

This deliverable addresses the first four episodes of the *Virtual Lecture Series Innovation*. This European lecture series encouraged a wide and critical understanding of innovation – from incremental to disruptive types of innovation, from technological to social innovations. It gave voice to various stakeholders from academia and industry within the innovation sphere that highlight different aspects of innovation. Topics so far include:

- Innovation and Uncertainty (University of Jena)
- Sustainable and Circular Entrepreneurship (University of Pavia)
- Social Innovation (University of Poitiers)
- Industry-university collaboration (University of Turku).

The *Virtual Lecture Series Innovation* aimed at different target groups – interested citizens, students, and professionals from university and industry. In total, the lecture series reached more than 200 interested people.

B. Overview of lectures

Date, time (CET), and platform	Host EC2U team	Episode Number and Title	Speaker	No of participants ¹
23.09.2021, 15:00-16:00 In Zoom	UJ	Episode 1: Innovation – so important but hard to predict or On how to outsmart uncertainty	Prof. Dr. Uwe Cantner , professor of microeconomics, Vice President for Young Researchers and Diversity Management at the University of Jena, and chairman of the Expert Commission on Research and Innovation (EFI) of the German federal government	22 (+137)
18.01.2022, 16:00-17:30 In Zoom	UNIPV	Episode 2 : Sustainable and Circular Entrepreneurship	Beatrice Re , post-doctoral researcher at the University of Pavia Alberto Bressan as special guest, founder of the circular fashion company SEAY	96 (+146)
15.6.2022, 15:00-17:00 On YouTube	UP	Episode 3: Social Innovation: The dynamics of companies, society and territories towards social innovations	Prof. Dominique Royoux , professor of geography and Co-Chairman of the Joint Research Unit “DESTINS” Ursula Dechein , research engineer at “DESTINS” and Sébastien Palluault Co-funder of the Company “Ellyx” and Member of the Executive Committee of “DESTINS”	20 (+188)
13.12.2022, 10:00-11:00 In Zoom	UTU	Episode 4: A new level in industry-university collaboration: The Entrepreneurs in Residence (EiR) programme at the University of Turku	Laura Strömberg , Founder and CEO of Dagsmark Petfood, EiR. Jussi Karttila , Founder and CEO of Zefort, EiR. Jarna Heinonen , Professor of Entrepreneurship. Sanna Ilonen , University teacher in Entrepreneurship	20
May/June 23	UC			
Nov/Dec 23	USAL			
May/June 24	UAIC			

¹ Number of live participants plus number of views on Youtube by January 2023

The Lecture Series is available on Youtube:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8TwRtegBBG0&list=PLfrwWJbjVZExCi6fJPmamvTfgZzPUsgoq>

Figure 1 : Exemplary visual impression of the series on Youtube

II. Feedback

In every episode, the audience was asked to fill in the feedback survey. In total, 30 feedback answers were submitted (see Annex). In average, 4.6 stars out of 5 stars were given. All answers had 3 or more stars, which shows the high satisfaction rate.

To develop the series further, we asked about “What could be improved?” and “What topics would you like to see in the following episodes? What questions about innovation should be discussed?”. Some examples in the answers were that more visualisation would have been helpful or that Innovative Education would be an interesting topic for a next episode.

III. Promotion

All episodes were promoted by many different channels: Each Virtual Lecture *Innovation* (VLS) was promoted on ec2u.eu with a news page. In addition, some local university websites had it as event (e.g. uni-jena.de). And social media (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram) was used— not only by the official EC2U account, also the universities, the board members and the city communities promoted the event via their networks. Please see the Annex for some examples.

Figure 2: Collage of Announcements on Websites

Each Lecture has its own key visual in a similar design: an illustration on light blue ground, with dotted yellow line, and people interacting with one symbol (telescope, recycle arrow, yellow heart, rug, etc). The people illustrations are designed by Pablo Stanley (CC0 license), the overall collage was built by Eleonore Roderfeld according to the topic of the lecture.

The target group was not the same in all episodes. For example, the 2nd episode on Circular Entrepreneurship was targeted at students and was thus promoted among the participants of the EC2U Entrepreneurial Academy via mailing list and in the EC2U Entrepreneurial Academy Online Lectures. The 4th episode on the Entrepreneurs in Residence programme was more targeted to university managers, especially those who were working in the “Innovation and Transfer” Working Group that brainstormed on the next EC2U E+ proposal.

Figure 3 : The key visuals of the four episodes

IV. Sustainability

Besides being a one-time event, the lecture series aims to have a sustainable impact. The recordings will be available online for all interested people. The insights provided by the lectures will also contribute to the Recipes of Innovation publication (D5.5) and to a Best Practice

exchange between the EC2U cities and innovation actors. The episodes are also incorporated into the EC2U Entrepreneurial Academy.

Episode 2 on Circular Entrepreneurship has been embedded in the “Conference on the Future of Europe” under the category “Leading the way for a more sustainable future”. This platform was used to invite a broad audience from across Europe and to share the insights. After the lecture, the audience was invited to ask questions and to share their ideas in a survey. Many good and thoughtful answers were received and then structured for a report that was uploaded on the same platform (see Annex).

Here is the platform with the event and the report on the VLS2 on Circular Entrepreneurship:

<https://futureu.europa.eu/en/processes/GreenDeal/f/2/meetings/111343>

V. Annex

A. Selected examples - websites

The screenshot shows a webpage from the European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U). The header includes the EC2U logo and navigation links. The main banner features the text "RI4C2 – Join the 1st episode of the Virtual Lecture Series 'Innovation'" with an illustration of a person looking through a telescope. Below the banner, the page content includes a title, a 3-minute reading time, social sharing buttons for Facebook and Twitter, and a detailed announcement. The announcement states that the first episode of the RI4C2 "Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens" lecture series will be held virtually on 23 September, at 15:00h. It also mentions that the lecture series is part of the project RI4C2, which aims to expand the activities of the EC2U Alliance. A photo of Prof. Dr. Uwe Cantner is included. The text further explains that the virtual lecture series will span the duration of the project until mid-2024, featuring top experts from research and industry. It specifies that the series kicks off on September 23rd with Prof. Dr. Uwe Cantner, a professor of microeconomics and Vice President for Young Researchers and Diversity Management at the University of Jena. The announcement concludes with the date and time of the lecture: "The lecture is held in English and open to the public. You are invited to join us on Zoom, on 23 September, 15:00-16:00 CEST:" followed by a Zoom link: <https://uni-jena-de.zoom.us/j/69096374414> (code: innovation).

VLS1 invitation on [www.ec2u.eu](https://ec2u.eu) (<https://ec2u.eu/ri4c2-join-the-1st-episode-of-the-virtual-lecture-series-innovation/>)

RI4C2 „Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens” lecture series

The 4th episode of the RI4C2 „Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens” lecture series will be held virtually on **December 13th, at 10:00 CET**. You are invited to join!

This time, the focus will be on a **new level in industry-university collaboration: The Entrepreneurs in Residence (EIR) programme at the University of Turku**. This programme systemically increases the participation and presence of active entrepreneurs in the school. On one hand, the EIRs offer students and researchers a direct connection to the realms of business life. On the other hand, entrepreneurs become familiar with university activities and students as well as get access to recent scholarly expertise. The unique programme started in autumn 2020 and is the first and only such collaborative programme between entrepreneurs and a university in Finland. ([More information on the programme.](#))

The aim of this panel discussion is to introduce the programme, its potential mutual benefits, share related experiences, and to discuss future developmental ideas.

Speakers

<p>Laura Strömberg, Founder and CEO of Dagsmark Petfood, EIR</p> <p>Jussi Karttila, Founder and CEO of Zefort, EIR</p> <p>Jarna Heinonen, Professor of Entrepreneurship</p> <p>Sanna Ilonen, University teacher in Entrepreneurship</p>	
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VLS4 event invitation on the UAIC website

Virtual Lecture Innovation - Social Innovation
Die dritte Episode der RI4C2-Vorlesungsreihe wird am 15. Juni stattfinden.

Zur Übersicht

DIESE VERANSTALTUNG IST BEENDET.	
Beginn	15. Juni 2022, 15:00 Uhr
Ende	15. Juni 2022, 17:00 Uhr
Veranstaltungsart	EC2U
Veranstaltungssprache	Englisch
Veranstaltungswebseite	Mehr erfahren
Barrierefreier Zugang	ja
Öffentlich	ja

Die dritte Episode der RI4C2-Vortragsreihe wird am 15. Juni um 15 Uhr MEZ virtuell stattfinden. Sie sind herzlich eingeladen, daran teilzunehmen!

Die virtuelle Vortragsreihe von RI4C2 zum Thema Innovation wird fortgesetzt. Der nächste Vortrag findet am 15. Juni mit Prof. Dominique Royoux, Professor für Geographie und Ko-Vorsitzender der Gemeinsamen Forschungsstelle „DESTINS“, Frau Ursula Dechein, Forschungsgemeinschaft bei „DESTINS“ und Herrn Sébastien Palluaud, Mitgründer des Unternehmens „Ela“, und Mitglied des Exekutivsausschusses von „DESTINS“ statt. In einem Vortrag mit dem Titel „Soziale Innovation: Die Dynamik der Unternehmen, der Gesellschaft und der Gebiete im Hinblick auf soziale Innovationen“ werden die drei Vertreter von DESTINS darüber sprechen, wie die sozialwissenschaftliche Forschung über das Tor dieser öffentlich-privaten Partnerschaft zu Lösungen für reale Probleme führen kann.

Der Vortrag wird in englischer Sprache gehalten und ist öffentlich zugänglich. Sie sind eingeladen, am 18. Januar 2022, 16:00-17:30 Uhr MEZ, via Zoom teilzunehmen.

Diese Veranstaltung ist Teil des RI4C2-Projekts „Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens“ der EC2U-Allianz, das von Horizon 2020 der Europäischen Kommission kofinanziert wird. Unsere virtuelle Vortragsreihe wird sich über die Dauer des Projekts bis Mitte 2024 erstrecken, in der Top-Experten aus Forschung und Industrie aus allen europäischen EC2U-Partnerstädten ein breites und kritisches Verständnis von Innovation fördern werden.

Die erste Folge der Vortragsreihe trug den Titel „Innovation – so wichtig, aber schwer vorhersehbar oder Wie man die Unsicherheit überflutet“ von Prof. Dr. Cantner von der Universität Jena. Die zweite Episode war mit Beatrice Re über Circular Entrepreneurship. Die Videoaufzeichnungen sind bei [YouTube](#) verfügbar.

15 June 2022
15:00-17:00 CET
Virtual Lecture Series Innovation
Social Innovation
Prof. Dominique Royoux, Ursula Dechein & Sébastien Palluaud
DESTINS

VLS3 event invitation in German, on the website of the University of Jena

B. Selected examples – social media

VLS4 invitation by EC2U LinkedIn account

VLS1 as LinkedIn event invitation

The university of Jena on twitter

VLS2 invitation as instagram-reel at the EC2U account

Invitation to watch the episodes as recordings on Youtube, by EC2U account on Instagram

JENA - Lichtstadt
21. September um 12:05 · Jena · 🌐

Sie interessieren sich für das Thema #Innovationen? Dann klicken Sie sich am 23. September in die Online-Vorlesung ein! Die [Universität Jena](#) startet neues Projekt zu Innovationen mit europäischer Allianz #EC2U.

- 👉 Wann? 23.09.2021, 15 - 16:00 Uhr, per Zoom
- 👉 Weitere Infos und Zoom-Link über den QR-Code oder: <https://uni-jena-de.zoom.us/j/69096374414>; Code: innovation
- 👉 Veranstaltung ist auf Englisch und öffentlich zugänglich
- 👉 ... Mehr ansehen — hier: [Universität Jena](#).

Virtuelle Vorlesungsreihe über "Innovationen"
Start am 23.09.2021

Neues Projekt der Uni Jena mit europäischer Allianz EC2U

5

VLS1 facebook post of the City of Jena, in German

← **Tweet**

Ludovic THILLY
@LThilly_CG

Delighted to chair 3rd #RI4C2 Virtual Lecture Series @EC2U_Alliance @UnivPoitiers on "Social Innovation" it is KEY to promote interdisciplinary research that includes SSH to find solutions to society challenges! #StrongerTogether

CONVICTION THAT THE LEVERS FOR THIS RENEWAL EXIST

- Support citizens' initiatives
- Put into account the diversity of positions
- COOPERATION ACTION COMMITTEES
- PUTTING POLITICAL AND SCIENTIFIC CONTEMPERES INTO PERSPECTIVE
- Support through legislation tools
- Create sustainable links between public, socio-economic and scientific actors
- PROJECT ENGINEERING
- KNOWLEDGE ACTIVATION
- INCREASE IN COMPETENCES

EC2U
European Comrn of City-Universi

EC2U Alliance of European Universities @EC2U_Alliance · 15 juin

🔔 Starting now !! The #RI4C2 Virtual Lecture Series episode on #SocialInnovation

Follow the live session on Youtube 📺 youtube.com/watch?v=BM17KM...

@UniTurku @UnivPoitiers @unipv @UniJena @usal @UnivdeCoimbra @UAICiasi

VLS3 tweet during session, by Ludovic Thilly, coordinator of EC2U Alliance

C. "Conference on the Future of Europe" platform

VLS2 on Circular Entrepreneurship was promoted and disseminated via the "Conference on the Future of Europe" platform:

<https://futureu.europa.eu/en/processes/GreenDeal/f/2/meetings/111343>

Conference on the Future of Europe

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Climate change and the environment

#TheFutureIsYours ● Leading the way for a more sustainable future

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Sustainable and Circular Entrepreneurship

Eleonore Roderfeld

12/01/2022 11:54 ● 1 comment

Event report available

We face global challenges stemming from the overexploitation of natural resources. Beatrice Re's lecture on "Sustainable and Circular Entrepreneurship" presents a path towards the circular economy via circular business models. Beatrice Re is a post-doctoral researcher at the University of Pavia, who spend the last years investigating sustainable entrepreneurship.

We are happy to have Alberto Bressan as special guest, to share his motivation and experience as founder of the circular fashion company SEAY.

The lecture is held in English and open to the public. After the lecture, the audience is invited to ask questions and to share their ideas in a survey.

This event is part of the RI4C2 "Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens" project of the EC2U Alliance, co-funded by Horizon 2020 of the European Commission. Further Virtual Lectures will also feature top experts from our EC2U partner cities to jointly promote a broad and critical understanding of innovation.

Go to the event's website [↗](#)

Using resources efficiently for a circular economy

18

January 2022

16:00 - 17:30

Join event

Number of participants

84

▲ 993 | Follow

Reference: cofe-MEET-2022-01-111343

Version number 6 (of 6) [see other versions](#)

[↗ Share](#)

[↗ Embed](#)

EVENT REPORT

The event was quite successful with an audience of 80 international citizens (including many students). After the input session, the audience asked many questions to Beatrice Re and Alberto Bressan. At the end, the participants were asked to give feedback and to share ideas in an online form. Posed question: "After this lecture, what are your ideas regarding circular economy? Where do you see the greatest potential of the EU economy to become more sustainable? How can single citizens support this endeavour?" The answers were collected online and grouped under "Citizen level" and "Institutional level". // CITIZEN LEVEL "Single citizens should try to upcycle their clothes. Moreover they have the moral obligation to be well informed on waste (not only regarding the fashion industry) and improve their shopping habits, also in the technological devices and grocery purchases. Trying to reduce their environmental footprint." "We have to make the right choices as consumers to create demand for circular products." "I think the CE can be implemented into any business, the real matter is to change the mindset of consumers so that this implementation is not perceived as a loss of buying power but more so as a way to buy smarter for us and for the planet." "Single citizens can support this endeavour by educating themselves for sustainable solutions for food, and transport, like citizens can be encouraged to grow their own food to make cities more greener and pleasing." // INSTITUTIONAL LEVEL "As for this presentation recycling used clothing products is advancing in the right way. In hopes that different sectors follow through." "Circular economy sounds good but I see some issues in it's global implementation. In the sector leisure transport like private jets/yachts EU economy can become more sustainable if tax these things for carbon emissions." "If products would be designed in a way that makes repairing and recycling easier, household consumption could become much more sustainable." "Circular economy has a great potential but is under-estimated and people are reluctant to invest as they see a lot of risks and difficult track to follow (at least for the beginning)." "For sure single citizen can opt for more sustainable choices in their everyday life preferring second hand's items and minimizing its consumption of plastic, on the other hand EU will have to finance and support more and more start-ups, companies and organization that are adopting a circular economy/are active on the front of sustainability and recycling." "Hearing about a company which is interested in recycling garments even if this doesn't bring a profit gave me hope for the future of the Planet and inspired me. The Growing Circular topic is very interesting and it would be great to see cooperation between political parties and big corporations towards this goal. Maybe reducing taxation and improving incentives for companies which are certified and act according to the Circular Business Model."

1 COMMENT

Sort by: Older ▾

Eleonore Roderfeld 28/01/2022 17:46

A video recording of the lecture is available here: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLfrwWJbjVZExCi6fJPMamvTfgZzPUsgoq>

D. Table of feedback

E: Number of episode

Star: Number of stars in a 5-star rating system

E	★	What could be improved?	What topics would you like to see in the following episodes?	Background
1	5		Social Innovations / Social Entrepreneurship	Professional (at university) from Germany
1	5	It was just excellent!	How to accompany researchers towards innovation/transfer of knowledge, how to build an innovative strategy for innovation	Professional (at university) from France
1	3	An concrete example on how uncertainty was outsmarted.	Absolute first steps.	Interested citizen from Germany
2	5			Student from Italy
2	5	More time for questions	The cost of 'circular' product	Student from Italy
2	5			Professional (at university) from Germany
2	4			Student from other
2	4	was good the interaction among speakers	digital devices in education	Professional (at university) from Italy
2	5			Student from Portugal
2	5	Very good		Student from Portugal
2	5			Student from Romania
2	5		More about fashion industry and how to develop it	Student from Romania
2	5	Maybe the possibility to ask questions with the mic		Student from other
2	5	Nothing. It was enough.	futuristic inventions that advances human species	Student from France

2	4	More audiovisual input		Student from Germany
2	5	Audio/Visual Aids	monetary system innovation in circular economy	Student from Italy
2	5		AI's impact in future professions, what will they be? what new skills will be needed?	Student from Italy
2	5		Greenwashing, how to detect it. Company cases where it is real Growing Circular vs Greenwashing	Interested citizen from Italy
2	5		Social innovation	Professional (non-university) from Italy
3	4	Some questions were not properly answered by the speakers. However, it is difficult to foresee the difficulty of the question.	More about social innovation in other universities, since the last lecture was focus on the French side.	Professional (at university) from France
3	4	They should have talked more about the concept of social innovation.	Social innovation under the prism of other countries	Interested citizen from France
3	5	Number of attendees face to face.	Disruptive innovation	Professional (at university) from Spain
3	3	120min is too long for such an input, I think. Moreover, slides and interactive parts would help to follow the lecture.	The threats of the growth/progress paradigm, that often comes with the innovation term.	Student from Germany
4	5			Professional (at university) from Germany
4	4	Names and companies of the people could be on the table		Professional (at university) from Finland
4	5		How can we stimulate innovativeness?	Professional (at university) from Romania
4	5	Slides and visualisation for the input part	e.g. innovative education - how to embed innovation and exploration at university teachings	Professional (at university) from Germany
4	4	Wider marketing of the events	University-business collaboration in R&D	Professional (at university) from Finland

4	4	It can be nice to use sometimes a presentation to show the results of the program	Discussion of inspiring and successful example of the start-up launch, track from the idea until IPO	Professional (at university) from France
4	4	some slides		Professional (at university) from Germany

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